

THE EFFECT OF MACHINING PARAMETERS ON SURFACE ROUGHNESS OF MEDIUM CARBON STEEL OF 0.3%C DURING TURNING OPERATIONS ON LATHE MACHINE USING FULL FACTORIAL DESIGN

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16925947>

Keywords:
full factorial design;
0.3%1C steel;
Machining;
Effect; surface roughness;
ANOVA.

Abstract: *The Effect of Machining Parameters on Surface Roughness of Medium Carbon Steel of 0.3%C during Turning Operation on Lathe Machine using Full Factorial Design was investigated. The data used for the work was from an earlier research titled "effect of machining parameters on the surface roughness of medium carbon steel using lathe machine". These data points were used to perform the analyses in full factorial design. In the factorial design analysis, the design type selected for this study was the full factorial design. As applicable with the response surface method, the same Design Expert (version 13.0.5.0) Minitab software package for design of experiments was used to analyse and generate model equation for surface roughness. The selected model for this design was the two factorial interaction (2FI). Based on this design, one hundred and twenty-five (125) data points, extracted from the five hundred (500) data points were used to perform the analysis. The result revealed that a mathematical model was developed for the prediction of surface roughness of 0.3%C steel during turning operation on the Lathe machine using full factorial design. It was observed that the predicted values of surface roughness were virtually the same with that of the actual values obtained from the experiment. ANOVA result of the model revealed that the "Model F-value" of 9300.94 implies the model was significant. Predicted R^2 of 0.9996 was in reasonable agreement with the Adjusted R^2 of 0.9998; i.e. the difference was less than 0.2. Adeq. Precision measures the signal to noise ratio. A ratio greater than 4 is desirable. Therefore, the ratio of 442.465 indicated an adequate signal implying that the model can be used to navigate the design space. The result also showed that interaction between cutting speed and feed rate was a slow steady increase as values of cutting parameters were being increased from 0.15rev/min to 0.21rev/min. Finally, the result from full factorial design was supported by the result from ANN, that feed rate has the highest influence or effect on surface roughness of 0.3%C steel during turning operation on the lathe machine. Full factorial design therefore can be used*

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for determining the effect of machining parameters on 0.3%C steel during turning operations on lathe machine.

1. INTRODUCTION

Antony (2014), clearly noted that factorial designs allows an experimenter to study the joint effect of the factors (or process/design parameters) on a response. This directly implies that factorial designs are most efficient and needed where many experiments involve the study of the effect of two or more factors on a given response. In factorial design, all possible combinations of the levels of the factors are investigated in each replication. For instance, if there are 'a' levels of factor X and 'b' levels of factor Y, then each replicate contains all 'ab' treatment combinations. A factorial design can either be full or fractional factorial design (Antony, 2014).

A full factorial experiment is an experiment whose design consist of two or more factors each with discreet possible values or levels and whose experimental units take on all possible combinations of these levels across all such factors. A full factorial design may also be termed a fully-crossed design. Such experiment or set of experiments, allows the researcher to study the effect of each factor on the response variable as well as the effects of interactions between factors on the response variable (Wiley, 2005). It must be noted that for the vast majority of factorial experiments, each factor has only two levels. For instance, with two factors each taking two levels, a factorial experiment would have four treatment

combinations in total, and this is usually referred to as a 2×2 factorial design. However, situations may arise where the number of combinations in a full factorial design is too high to be reasonably plausible, then a fractional factorial design may be carried out. In this case, some of the possible combinations (usually up to half) are neglected. Steel is a very essential component in our day to day lives. Applications of steel can be found in the production of axles, gears and crankshafts which are important parts in the automobile industry. Steel usage is also predominant in the fabrication of rods and support structures in the building and construction industry. Critical components of aircrafts in the aviation industry also employ steel as a major material used in the production of various parts. Steel also finds its uses in domestic settings as they are usually used in the fabrication of burglary proofs, kitchen equipment, security architecture of smart houses as well as household furniture and fittings. The different areas where steel finds its uses is inexhaustible. Basically, the different type of steels are carbon steels, stainless steels, alloy steels and tool steels (Wente *et al.*, 2019).

The surface integrity of a machined part encompasses all primary, standard and extended information related to the quality of a solid surface. An important parameter of surface integrity is surface roughness and it is the measure of macro and micro asperities and

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irregularities on a finished surface after machining (Astakhov, 2020). Basic industrial requirements of machined parts such as appearance, corrosion resistance, wear resistance, fatigue resistance, lubrication, tolerances and ability to hold pressure, can very well be linked to the quality of surface roughness (Liao *et al.*, 2021).

In machining operations, different machine tools such as lathes, drilling machine, horizontal and vertical milling machines etc., are utilised. Of these machining processes, turning still remains the most important operation used to shape metal, because in turning, the conditions of operation are most varied in the modern industry (Pankaj *et al.*, 2017).

The objective of this paper is to investigate the effect of machining parameters on surface roughness of 0.3%C steel which has been turned

using lathe machine under different cutting parameters using full factorial design.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 Materials

The main material used for this work was steel samples. The steel samples were analysed at the Defence Industry Corporation of Nigeria, (DICON), Kaduna. Results obtained from this analysis indicated that the selected work-piece contain 0.3% carbon indicating a medium carbon category. Other materials and tools used in this research work include data from previous work on effect of machining parameters on the surface roughness of medium carbon steel using lathe machine (Sam, *et al.*, 2024), Microsoft Excel, and Design Expert (version 13.0.5.0) Minitab software package for design of experiments. Table 1 shows the data that was obtained from the previous work.

Table 2.1: Selected cutting parameters with respective values of surface roughness.

Cutting (rpm)	Speed	Feed Rate (mm/rev)	Depth of Cut (mm)	Mean Surface Roughness (µm)	Surface Value
55		0.15	0.25	1.62	
55		0.21	0.35	2.20	
200		0.15	0.75	0.52	
200		0.21	0.35	3.79	
300		0.15	0.25	1.43	
300		0.21	0.75	0.95	

2.2 Method

The data in Table 2.1 was further expanded using the “Rand function” in Microsoft Excel. Five hundred (500) data points were generated

from the original data using this function. These data points were used to perform the analyses in full factorial design.

2.2.1 Factorial design

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In the factorial design analysis, the design type selected for this study was the full factorial design. As applicable with the response surface method, the same Design Expert (version 13.0.5.0) Minitab software package for design of experiments was used to analyse and generate model equation for surface roughness. The selected model for this design was the two factorial interaction (2FI). Based on this design,

one hundred and twenty-five (125) data points, extracted from the five hundred (500) data points were used to perform the analysis.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Results on factorial design

The results on the analysis of variance of the selected design model (2FI) is presented in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: ANOVA for the selected factorial model (Response = Surface Roughness)

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	4.31	60	0.0718	9300.94	< 0.0001	significant
A-Cutting Speed	0.3994	4	0.0998	12942.41	< 0.0001	
B-Feed Rate	2.40	4	0.5999	77765.58	< 0.0001	
C-Depth of Cut	1.42	4	0.3559	46133.18	< 0.0001	
AB	0.0723	16	0.0045	585.45	< 0.0001	
AC	0.0016	16	0.0001	13.10	< 0.0001	
BC	0.0086	16	0.0005	69.68	< 0.0001	
Residual	0.0005	64	7.714E-06			
Cor. Total	4.31	124				

The “Model F-value” of 9300.94 implies the model is significant. There is only a 0.01% chance that an F-value this large could occur due to noise. P-values less than 0.0500 indicate model terms are significant. In this case A, B, C, AB, AC, BC are significant model terms. Values greater than 0.1000 indicate the model terms are not significant. If there are many insignificant model terms (not counting those required to support hierarchy), model reduction may improve the model. The Predicted R² of 0.9996 is in reasonable agreement with the Adjusted R² of

0.9998; i.e. the difference is less than 0.2. Adeq. Precision measures the signal to noise ratio. A ratio greater than 4 is desirable. Therefore, the ratio of 442.465 indicates an adequate signal implying that the model can be used to navigate the design space.

3.2 Effect of machining parameters on surface roughness using full factorial design

In Table 3.1, it is observed that the F-values of feed rate, depth of cut and cutting speed were 77765.58, 46133.18 and 12942.41 respectively.

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This shows that the most significant parameter affecting surface roughness is feed rate. This is because the F-values is a ratio of variation between sample means to variation within sample means. The higher the F-value, the better the model. From the F-values, the next significant value affecting surface roughness is the depth of cut and lastly, the cutting speed. The result recorded here is partly in agreement with the works of Rafai and Islam (2009), Singh *et al.* (2013), Das *et al.* (2013), Abdullah *et al.* (2008),

$$SR = 3.204 - 1.64 \times 10^{-3}CS - 1.55 \times 10^{-2}FR - 6.5 \times 10^{-3}DC - 1.56 \times 10^{-3}CS \times FR - 1.52 \times 10^{-3}CS \times DC - 1.23 \times 10^{-4}FR \times DC - 435 \times 10^{-1}CS \times FR \times DC$$

Equation 3.1

In Figure 3.1, it can be observed that the predicted values of surface roughness are virtually the same with that of the actual values

Surface Roughness

Color points by value of Surface Roughness:
1.315 2.184

Rao *et al.* (2013), Kumar, *et al.* (2013), Prasad *et al.* (2013; Zeqiri *et al.*, 2018), who documented that feed rate had the most significant effect on surface roughness values.

The final regression equation in terms of actual factors for this model is given below:

obtained from the experiment. This shows that Equation 3.1 satisfies the conditions necessary to correctly predict the surface roughness of 0.3%C steel (medium carbon steel).

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Figure 3.1: Predicted vs Actual Values

The interaction plot for the surface roughness values (Figure 3.2) indicates the behavioural pattern of the cutting parameters as it interacts with each other in the cutting process. The interaction between cutting speed and feed rate shows a slow steady increase as values of cutting parameters are being increased from 0.15rev/min to 0.21rev/min. This interaction is proportional to the slow steady increase in the values of surface roughness. An almost similar effect is observed in the interaction between cutting speed and depth of cut as the values of both parameters increases. However, a near uniform cut is observed between feed rate and the depth of cut as they interact with each other

in the cutting process. Initially, at lower values, there appears to be a lagging in the cutting parameters with corresponding lower surface roughness values, but a rapid rise is observed as the values of the interacting cutting parameters increases. The main effects plot of the cutting parameters for the surface roughness is shown in Figure 3.3 and it is a corroboration of the already established fact that feed rate has the most significant influence on the surface roughness of medium carbon steel. This means that increasing the feed rate will also result in a corresponding increase in the values of surface roughness. This is followed by depth of cut and cutting speed as evidenced in the main effect plot.

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Figure 3.2: Interaction plot for surface roughness

Figure 3.3: Main effects plot for surface roughness

Source: Field data (2021)

3.3 Comparison of the results obtained from ANN, RSM and Factorial Design

A presentation of the comparison of the results obtained from the three analytical methods is given in Table 3.3. The effect of machining

parameters on the surface roughness of medium carbon steel is categorised based on their order of significance. The parameter with the highest significance is assigned a value of “1” while the parameter with the least significance is assigned a value of “3”. The parameter with an intermediary effect is assigned a value of “2”.

Table 3.2: Comparison of results obtained from the three analytical methods

		1	2	3	Supporting Works
Analytical Methods					
Artificial Neural Network (ANN)	Feed rate	Cutting Speed	Depth of cut	Abdullah <i>et al.</i> (2008), Rao <i>et al.</i> (2013), Das <i>et al.</i> (2013), Kumar <i>et al.</i> (2013), Prasad (2013), Singh <i>et al.</i> (2013), Rafai and Islam (2009), Senthil <i>et al.</i> (2013)	
Central Composite Design of RSM	Cutting speed	Depth of cut	Feed rate	Zeqiri <i>et al.</i> (2018) only attested to the fact that increasing depth of cut resulted in a corresponding increase of roughness parameters.	
Factorial Interactions of Factorial Design	Feed rate	Depth of cut	Cutting Speed	Abdullah <i>et al.</i> (2008), Rao <i>et al.</i> (2013), Das <i>et al.</i> (2013), Kumar <i>et al.</i> (2013), Prasad (2013), Singh <i>et al.</i> (2013), Rafai and Islam (2009), Senthil <i>et al.</i> (2013)	

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The three analytical method from Table 3.2 show that the most significant machining parameter for Artificial Neural Network is feed rate, for Central Composite Design of RSM it is cutting speed, while, for Factorial Interactions of Factorial Design it is feed rate. Both artificial neural network and factorial interactions of factorial design all have feed rate as the most significant machining parameter. The result from Central Composite Design of RSM has cutting speed as the most significant machining parameter in contrast to the two analytical methods. The result from full factorial design therefore is supported by the result from ANN that feed rate has the highest influence or effect on surface roughness of 0.3%C steel during turning operation on the lathe machine. This position is also documented by several researchers (Aman and Hari, 2005; Abdullah *et al.*, 2008; Alabi *et al.*, 2010; Kumar *et al.*, 2013; Singh *et al.*, 2013; Sam, 2024; Sam, *et al.*, 2024).

4. CONCLUSION

The work “the determination of effect of machining parameters on surface roughness of 0.3%C steel turned on Lathe machine using full factorial design” was carried out and the following conclusions were drawn from the study:

1. A mathematical model was developed for the prediction of surface roughness of 0.3%C steel during turning operation on the Lathe machine using full factorial design.
2. It was observed that the predicted values of surface roughness were virtually the same with

that of the actual values obtained from the experiment.

3. ANOVA result of the model revealed that the “Model F-value” of 9300.94 implies the model is significant.
4. Predicted R^2 of 0.9996 is in reasonable agreement with the Adjusted R^2 of 0.9998; i.e. the difference is less than 0.2.
5. Adeq. Precision measures the signal to noise ratio. A ratio greater than 4 is desirable. Therefore, the ratio of 442.465 indicates an adequate signal implying that the model can be used to navigate the design space.
6. The interaction between cutting speed and feed rate shows a slow steady increase as values of cutting parameters are being increased from 0.15rev/min to 0.21rev/min.
7. Finally, the result from full factorial design is supported by the result from ANN, that feed rate has the highest influence or effect on surface roughness of 0.3%C steel during turning operation on the lathe machine.

Author Contribution

This is to publicly declare that the four authors of this publication (names listed above) were involved in the conceptualization of this research topic. Mr. Emmanuel .U. Odeh, the first author was saddled with the responsibility of data curation and assisted by the other three authors with formal analysis. No outside funding was received for this project. The major financial contributor to this project was the third author. The four authors were jointly involved in the research project; playing various roles as

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Irish International Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences

Irish J. Eng. A. Sci.

Volume: 9; Issue: 04,

July-August, 2025

ISSN: 2965-3325

Impact Factor: 4.84

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/ijjeas>

supervisors, investigators and resource providers to enable the project go through the various stages of conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, funding, investigation, methodology, project administration, resource provision, software provision, supervision, validation, writing original draft and final report, and final paper for publication. This was adopted by all the four members of the research team.

Funding

The members of this research team wish to publicly declare that this project was self-funded by team members.

Data Availability

The data used for this work is available in the University of Uyo, Uyo-Nigeria library, in the M.Eng.degree report submitted to the University. It is also available in journal publication made from the work. The references included in our journal publication are duly referenced. Every second party data used in the publication is duly referenced and credit given to source.

Conflict of Interests

The authors wish to publicly declare that there is no conflict of interest in this publication all the four authors have agreed to submit their work for journal publication.

Financial Interests

We wish to publicly declare that this is a self-sponsored research work contributed to by the research team members.

Non-Financial Interests

This work is free of all encumbrances, whether financial or non-financial interests

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Irish International Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences

Irish J. Eng. A. Sci.

Volume: 9; Issue: 04,

July-August, 2025

ISSN: 2965-3325

Impact Factor: 4.84

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<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/ijjeas>

<https://www.digitaltrends.com/cool-tech/what-is-an-artificial--neural-network/> (Retrieved on May 11, 2018)
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